

Precisely Patterned Nanofibers for
High Performance Bioseparations

DELIVERABLE 2.2.

BIOPRODUCTION OF
UNMODIFIED
SPIDROIN

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Website: <https://pure-fetopen.eu>

Add creator: Charlotte Leonhardt

Add contributor(s): Johannes Diehl, Andreas Schmidt, Prof. Dr. Thomas Scheibel

Abbreviations

Abbreviation / Acronym	
eADF4	engineered <i>Araneus diadematus</i> fibroin 4
m/z	mass-to-charge
MALDI-TOF	Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization - Time of Flight
PURE	Precisely Patterned Nanofibers for High Performance Bioseparations
UV/Vis	ultraviolet/visible
WP	Work Package

I. Introduction

Deliverable 2.2 includes at least 500 mg of the unmodified spidroins eADF4(C16), eADF4(Ω 16) and eADF4(κ 16), respectively. These recombinantly produced spidroins contain a T7-Tag for immunodetection and 16 repetitions of the so-called C-module, resulting in a molecular weight of ca. 48 kDa. [1] eADF4(C16) represents the negatively charged protein variant, while eADF4(Ω 16) possesses a neutral and eADF4(κ 16) a positive charge. The amino acid sequence, fermentation, and purification process of all spidroin variants is already published [1-3]. Thus, this report presents the analysis of purified, unmodified spidroin variants, which serve as controls for the corresponding modified spidroins in the PURE project.

2. eADF4(C16)

The eADF4(C16) batch described here was labeled I2SSP01-037-001-015/019.

The purified protein was labeled with a N-hydroxysuccinimide-ester-conjugated fluorescein and analyzed by SDS-PAGE (Figure 1). The fluorescence-detected gel exhibited a clear protein band and weaker fluorescing degradation bands.

Figure 1: Fluorescein-labeled spidroin, analyzed by SDS-PAGE. 1: eADF4(C16); 2: Marker.

The UV/Vis spectra of dialyzed spidroins (Figure 2; I4 1 G & I4 2 G) showed the protein peak at ca. 280 nm (Figure 2).

Figure 2: UV/Vis-spectra of dialyzed spidroins.

Mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF method) revealed the presence of eADF4(C16) with a m/z ratio ($M+H^+$) of 47320 (Figure 3; C16 I3_I4_0_G3_I1).

Figure 3: MALDI-TOF mass spectra of spidroins.

3. eADF4(κI6)

The eADF4(κI6) batch described here was labeled 2020_16 (unified).

In SDS-PAGE analysis, there was a clear protein band appearing at ca. 50 kDa (Figure 4 A, line 4-8). Slight degradation bands were visible in samples 5 & 6, however the absence of other protein bands indicated that the spidroin was not contaminated by other proteins. The Western Blot with the anti-T7-antibody confirmed that the band at 50 kDa represented eADF4(κI6) (Figure 4 B).

Figure 4: Silver-stained SDS-PAGE gel (A) and Western Blot with an anti-T7-antibody (B). 1: Marker; 2: 2016_29_1; 3: 2020_14; 4: 2020_16_1; 5: 2020_16_2; 6: 2020_16_3; 7: 2020_16_4; 8: 2020_16_5.

The UV/Vis spectrum of purified and dialyzed spidroin is shown in Figure 5. The 260/280 nm absorption ratio was at 0.62, indicating a low contamination by nucleic acids.

Figure 5: UV/Vis-spectrum of dialyzed spidroin.

4. eADF4(Ω16)

The eADF4(Ω16) batch described here was labeled 2020_63_1.

In SDS-PAGE analysis, there was a clear protein band appearing at ca. 50 kDa (Figure 6 A). The absence of other protein bands indicated that the spidroin was not contaminated by other proteins and no degradation occurred. The Western Blot with the anti-T7-antibody confirmed that the band represented eADF4(Ω16) (Figure 6 B).

Figure 6: Silver-stained SDS-PAGE gel (A) and Western Blot with an anti-T7-antibody (B). 1: Marker; 2: eADF4(Ω16).

The UV/Vis spectrum of purified and dialyzed spidroin is shown in Figure 7. The 260/280 nm absorption ratio was at 0.66, indicating a low contamination by nucleic acids.

Figure 7: UV/Vis-spectrum of dialyzed spidroin.

5. Summary

The protein analyses demonstrated a reasonable purity of the spidroins. Over 500 mg of all three spidroin variants, respectively, are available.

6. References

1. Huebnerich, D., et al., *Primary structure elements of spider dragline silks and their contribution to protein solubility*. *Biochemistry*, 2004. **43**(42): p. 13604-13612.
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